

Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones. Part-IX. Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-(2'-Aryl-4-thiazolidinon-3'-yl)-4-(2''-methyl-4''-hydroxy-5''-isopropylphenyl)thiazoles

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Several new 4-thiazolidinones have been prepared bearing 2-amino-4-(2'-methyl-4'-hydroxy-5'-isopropylphenyl)thiazole moiety. Their structures have been supported by ir and mass spectral studies. The products have been screened for their antimicrobial activity.

4-Thiazolidinones¹ and thiazoles² are associated with various biological activities. With an intention to prepare more active drugs we have synthesised 4-thiazolidinone derivatives having thiazoles (4-6) by the action of thioglycolic, thiomalic and thiolactic acid, on Schiff bases obtained by condensing 2-amino-4-(2'-methyl-4'-hydroxy-5'-isopropylphenyl)-thiazole with different aromatic aldehydes.

Acetylthymol (1), prepared from thymol, was condensed with thiourea in presence of iodine to yield 2-amino-4-(2'-methyl-4'-hydroxy-5'-isopropylphenyl)thiazole (2). This on condensation with different aromatic aldehydes gave the Schiff bases (3a-t). The latter on further treatment with thioglycolic, thiolactic and thiomalic acids, gave substituted-4-thiazolidinones (4-6a-t).

The compounds were screened for antimicrobial and antifungal activity using cup-plate method³, using a concentration of 50 µg ml⁻¹ against bacterial strains of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citreus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* and fungal strains like *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger*. Most of the compounds were found moderately active (15-25 mm, zone of inhibition) against different strains of bacteria and fungi, when compared to standard compounds like ampicillin, tetracyclin, norfloxacin and cephalexin (15-27 mm) (antibacterial) and griseofulvin (23-25 mm) (antifungal).

The most active compounds were X = H and Ar = 2-aminophenyl (13-23 mm), 3-aminophenyl (18-22 mm), furyl (13-29 mm); when X = CH₃ and Ar = phenyl (15-17 mm), 2-chlorophenyl (14-21 mm), 2-nitrophenyl (15-21 mm), cinnamyl (14-22 mm), furyl (14-23 mm); and when X = CH₂COOH and Ar = phenyl (13-25 mm), 4-hydroxyphenyl (12-28 mm), 2-methoxyphenyl (12-20 mm), 2,4-dichlorophenyl (12-20 mm) and 3,4-dichlorophenyl (14-20 mm).

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectral (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 435 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a JEOL JMS-D 300 spectrometer.

4-Acetylthymol (1) and 2-amino-4-(2'-methyl-4'-hydroxy-5'-isopropylphenyl)thiazole (2) were prepared by the reported method^{4,5}.

2-Benzal-amino-4-(2'-methyl-4'-hydroxy-5'-isopropylphenyl)thiazole (3a-t) : A mixture of benzaldehyde (0.001 mol) and 2 (0.001 mol) in methanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. The product was isolated after cooling and crystallised from ethanol, (3a; 65%), m.p. 115° (Found : C, 71.13; H, 5.96; N, 8.29; S, 9.49. C₂₀H₁₂N₂OS calcd. for : C, 71.39; H, 5.99 ; N, 8.32 ; S, 9.52%); ν_{max} 1 610 (C=N), 1 410, 1 440, 700 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C thiazole); m/z 337 (M⁺), 336, 248, 233, 207, 206, 189, 177, 133, 105, 91, 77.

for 3-6
Ar

- | | |
|------------------------|--------------------------|
| a; Phenyl | k; 3,4-Dichlorophenyl |
| b; 4-Hydroxyphenyl | l; 3-Aminophenyl |
| c; 2-Methoxyphenyl | m; 4-Aminophenyl |
| d; 3-Methoxyphenyl | n; 2-Nitrophenyl |
| e; 4-Methoxyphenyl | o; 3-Nitrophenyl |
| f; 3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl | p; 4-Dimethylaminophenyl |
| g; 2-Chlorophenyl | q; Cinnamyl |
| h; 4-Chlorophenyl | r; Vanilline |
| i; 2,4-Dichlorophenyl | s; Furyl |
| j; 2,6-Dichlorophenyl | t; 2-Hydroxynaphthyl |

for 4: X = H
5; X = CH₃
6; X = CH₂COOH

Similarly, other Schiff bases (3b-t; yields 54-76%) were prepared : 3b, m.p. 198°; c, 188°; d, 223°; e, 138°; f, 102°; g, 140°; h, 142°; i, 104°; j, 101°; k, 174°; l, 108°; m, 122°; n, 112°; o, 131°; p, 173°; q, 111°; r, 115°; s, 142°; t, 118°.

2-(2'-Aryl-5'-H/methyl-4'-thiazolidinon-3'-yl)-4-(2''-methyl-4''-hydroxy-5''-isopropylphenyl)thiazoles (4a-t, 5a-t) : A mixture of thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol, 0.69 ml)/thiolactic acid (0.01 mol, 1.76 ml) and benzalamino-4-(2'-methyl-4'-hydroxy-5'-isopropylphenyl)thiazoles (0.01 mol, 3.36 g) was refluxed for 15 h at 110-120° in an oil-bath. Sodium bicarbonate solution added for removal of excess thioglycolic/ thiolactic acid. The product was isolated and crystallised : 4a (58%), m.p. 250° (Found : C, 64.17; H, 5.38; N, 6.80; S, 15.57. C₂₂H₂₂N₂O₂S₂ requires : C, 64.36; H, 5.4; N, 6.82; S, 15.61%); v_{max} 1 690 (C=O), 1 575 (C=N), 700 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); m/z 424 (M⁺), 363, 335, 248 (base peak), 232, 206, 189, 177, 133, 105, 91, 77. Similarly, compounds 4b-t (yields 54-74%) were prepared : 4b, m.p. 230°; c, 258°; d, 235°; e, 242°; f, 207°; g, 145°; h, 222°; i, 225°; j, 215°; k, 167°; l, 240°; m, 330°; n, 210°; o, 223°; p, 252°; q, 185°; r, 162°; s, 178°; t, 249°.

Compound 5a had (71%) m.p. 238° (Found : C, 64.67; H, 5.66; N, 6.55; S, 15.01. C₂₃H₂₄N₂O₂S₂ requires : C, 65.06; H, 5.69; N, 6.59; S, 15.01%); v_{max} 1 670 (C=O), 1 540 (C=N), 710 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C), m/z 424 (M⁺), 363, 335, 248, 232, 206, 189, 177, 133, 91, 77.

Similarly, compounds 5b-t (yields 57-71%) were prepared : 5b, m.p. 235°; c, 235°; d, 242°; e, 218°; f, 180°; g, 230°; h, 210°; i, 245°; j, 197°; k, 200°; l, 237°; m, 260°; n, 219°; o, 235°; p, 210°; q, 225°; r, 240°; s, 240°; t, 230°.

2-(2'-Aryl-5'-carboxymethyl)-4'-thiazolidinon-3'-yl)-4-(2''-methyl)-4''-hydroxy-5''-isopropylphenylthiazoles (6a-t) : The appropriate thiazole (3a-t; 0.01 mol) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.02 mol, 3.002 g) in presence of zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 h. The temperature was then raised to 180° for 30 min. The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution, reprecipitated with dilute HCl and crystallised from ethanol : 4a (38%), m.p. 158° (Found : C, 61.20; H, 5.13; N, 5.94; S, 13.61. C₂₄H₂₄N₂O₄S₂

requires : C, 61.51; H, 5.16; N, 5.97; S, 13.68%; ν_{\max} 3 400–3 300 (OH), 1 710 (C=O), 1 575 (–N), 700 (C–S–C), 1 280 cm^{-1} (C–O), m/z 468 (M^+), 391, 232, 160, 116, 84, 71, 57, 44 (base peak), 195, 163, 149, 133, 105, 91, 77. Similarly, compounds **6b–t** (yields 37–62%) were prepared : **6b**, m.p. 180°; **c**, 148°; **d**, 169°; **e**, 153°; **f**, 201°; **g**, 159°; **h**, 174°; **i**, 168°; **j**, 192°; **k**, 183°; **l**, 320°; **m**, 320°; **n**, 259°; **o**, 282°; **p**, 158°; **q**, 169°; **r**, 194°; **s**, 250°d; **t**, 201°.

All compounds gave satisfactory nitrogen analysis.

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